

Tarnavska Svitlana Ivanivna

Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor

Of the Department of Pediatrics and Children's Infectious Diseases

Snopkovska Valeriia Valeriivna

6th year student

Bukovyna State Medical University

Chernivtsi, Ukraine

Kipen Bohdan Volodymyrovych

6th year student

Bukovyna State Medical University

Chernivtsi, Ukraine

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18008708>

BRONCHIOLITIS IN CHILDREN: CLINICAL FEATURES AND DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS

Abstract.

The article discusses modern approaches to the diagnosis of bronchiolitis and highlights key aspects of differential diagnosis with bronchial asthma, pneumonia, foreign body obstruction, and other pathologies that can mimic similar symptoms.

Keywords: bronchiolitis, children, respiratory distress

Main part. Bronchiolitis is the leading cause of hospitalization in children under two years of age, especially in the winter and spring, when respiratory viruses are most prevalent [1]. The most common pathogen is respiratory syncytial virus (RSV), which causes most cases of bronchiolitis in children under one year of age [2].

Rhinovirus, metapneumovirus, influenza viruses, parainfluenza, and adenovirus infection can also cause the clinical picture of bronchiolitis, although the course is usually somewhat milder or atypical [3]. Risk factors for severe disease include prematurity, low birth weight, passive smoking, congenital heart defects, chronic lung disease, and immunodeficiency [2]. Premature infants are at increased risk of hospitalization due to immature bronchiolar structure, fewer alveoli, and immature immune response [1].

The pathogenesis of bronchiolitis is based on direct viral damage to the epithelial cells of the small airways, which causes inflammation, necrosis, and desquamation (peeling) of the ciliated epithelium [2]. The combination of submucosal edema, mucus hypersecretion, and accumulation of cellular debris leads to the formation of dense plugs and intraluminal obstruction of the bronchioles [3]. This causes a disruption in the breathing mechanism: complete obstruction contributes to the formation of atelectasis due to air absorption, while partial obstruction acts as a valve mechanism, causing air retention and hyperinflation of the lungs [1]. Hypoxia develops as a result of a pronounced ventilation-perfusion imbalance and serves as a key marker of disease severity [4].

The clinical picture of bronchiolitis usually begins with prodromal symptoms of upper respiratory tract involvement (rhinorrhea, cough), gradually followed by shortness of breath and wheezing [1]. Subsequently, tachypnea, wheezing, flaring of the nostrils, and involvement of the accessory muscles in breathing appear [2]. In infants, the initial symptom may be apnea,

which usually indicates a severe course and is an indication for immediate hospitalization [2]. Auscultation may reveal wheezing (wheezing), fine-bubbled moist rales, or general weakening of breathing with severe lung hyperinflation [1]. Increased respiratory load and associated feeding difficulties often lead to decreased appetite, lethargy, and increased risk of dehydration [4].

The diagnosis of bronchiolitis is based primarily on the clinical picture, the age of the child, and the characteristic symptoms of upper respiratory tract involvement and lower respiratory tract obstruction [2]. Routine chest X-rays are not recommended. Radiographic changes in bronchiolitis are usually nonspecific and may lead to the unjustified prescription of antibiotic therapy [1]. Virological diagnosis (PCR) is of auxiliary importance and is used mainly in severe cases or in hospital settings [3]. Pulse oximetry is a key element in assessing the severity of the condition, monitoring, and determining the need for oxygen therapy [4].

The differential diagnosis of bronchiolitis is extremely important, as a number of diseases in young children can be accompanied by similar respiratory symptoms, requiring timely differentiation in order to select the optimal therapeutic strategy [2]. The differential diagnosis of bronchiolitis is most often performed with pneumonia, bronchial asthma (BA), airway obstruction by a foreign body, recurrent wheezing syndrome, and heart failure [2].

Bronchial asthma often mimics bronchiolitis, especially in young children, where wheezing is a common symptom [1]. An important distinguishing feature is the recurrent nature of episodes of bronchial obstruction in bronchial asthma. In contrast, bronchiolitis is usually the first and only episode of acute obstruction in a child with no previous history of wheezing [2]. The presence of allergic manifestations or a family history of allergic diseases significantly favors a diagnosis of bronchial asthma [1]. Clinical improvement after the

use of bronchodilators is the most characteristic difference from bronchial asthma. In most children with bronchiolitis, these drugs do not provide a significant clinical effect [3].

It should be noted that after bronchiolitis, repeated episodes of wheezing (wheezing) are not always a sign of the development of bronchial asthma, but may reflect a prolonged post-infectious inflammatory process [5]. Such episodes of recurrent wheezing syndrome (RWS) may recur for months, but usually tend to gradually decrease in frequency and intensity, indicating the transient nature of the obstruction [5].

Pneumonia should be ruled out in all children with clear clinical and physical markers that distinguish it from bronchiolitis: high fever, focal auscultatory changes, namely, weakened breathing, moist rales, and dullness of percussion sound over the lesion [2]. Radiographically, pneumonia is characterized by segmental or partial infiltrates (consolidation). In contrast, uncomplicated bronchiolitis typically shows only signs of hyperinflation [1]. Bacterial pneumonia is more often accompanied by unilateral auscultatory changes and local crepitus, which is not characteristic of the diffuse process in bronchiolitis [3].

Aspiration of a foreign body usually manifests itself as a sudden onset of symptoms after an episode of suffocation or coughing and, unlike bronchiolitis, there is no catarrhal precursor [3]. The key physical signs are asymmetric breath sounds, unilateral ventilation impairment, or localized wheezing (wheezing), which fundamentally distinguishes this condition from diffuse viral damage in bronchiolitis [2]. In complex cases, bronchoscopy is used for accurate localization and confirmation of the diagnosis, which is both a diagnostic and therapeutic procedure for removing foreign bodies [4].

Although heart failure (HF) is less common, it can mimic severe bronchiolitis due to the presence of tachypnea, involvement of accessory muscles in breathing, and general difficulty breathing [1]. Unlike bronchiolitis, the key signs of cardiac pathology are the absence of febrile fever and the presence of hepatomegaly (enlargement of the liver), heart murmur or gallop rhythm on auscultation, as well as poor weight gain (or rapid fatigue during feeding) [2]. Radiographically, cardiomegaly and signs of venous congestion in the lungs are often found in HF, whereas hyperinflation is typical only in bronchiolitis. Echocardiography is a key tool for confirming the diagnosis of HF, as it allows the structure and function of the myocardium to be assessed [1].

Conclusion. Bronchiolitis in young children remains one of the leading causes of acute respiratory diseases and hospitalizations, underscoring its importance in modern pediatric practice. A thorough analysis of clinical manifestations and the use of modern diagnostic approaches help to avoid misdiagnosis and prevent unnecessary treatment.

List of references:

1. Bush A, Thomson AH. Acute bronchiolitis. *BMJ*. 2007;335(7628):1037-1041.
2. Øymar K, Skjerven HO, Mikalsen IB. Acute bronchiolitis in infants, a review. *Scand J Trauma Resusc Emerg Med*. 2014;22:23.
3. Angurana SK, Williams V, Takia L. Acute Viral Bronchiolitis: A Narrative Review. *J Pediatr Intensive Care*. 2020;12(2):79-86.
4. Cunningham S, Rodriguez A, Adams T, et al. Bronchiolitis. *F1000Prime Rep*. 2013;5:65.
5. Fan Y, Zhang P, Huang Y, et al. Risk factors for recurrent wheezing after bronchiolitis. *BMC Pediatr*. 2023;23:317.